

Insight of Al Hijamah Therapy among Allopathic Doctors of Karachi, Pakistan

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Abstract:

Aims and objectives: Complementary and Alternative Medicine (CAM) encompasses all forms of therapies that fall outside the mainstream of medical practice. Wet cupping, also known as Al Hijamah therapy, is recognized by the World Health Organization (WHO) as a prominent area within the realm of alternative medicine. Its increasing awareness among general population and misconceptions among allopathic doctors, highlights the need to assess the level of knowledge, attitude, and practices of physicians regarding this therapy to promote it effectively and safely in Pakistan.

Methodology: A cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted from January 2021 to Dec 2022 among allopathic doctors practicing in various hospitals and private clinics of Karachi, Pakistan. The survey was carried out using both hard copy and online questionnaire, which includes four sections: socio-demographics, knowledge of physicians toward cupping therapy, physicians' attitudes toward therapy, and physicians' practice toward al hijama therapy. IBM-SPSS version 23.0 was used for data analysis.

Results: Out of the 182 responses, 96.7% of the physicians were aware of al Hijamah therapy, 72% expressed a desire to acquire knowledge, 56.6% undergone this therapy and tend to integrate this therapy into their clinical practices. However only 34.8% of the physicians referred their patients to Hijamah therapists.

Conclusion: Our research findings suggest that physicians have a sound understanding of al hijama therapy and maintain a positive outlook toward it. Despite their proficiency in this field, physicians encounter obstacles in effectively employing, recommending, or referring patients to this therapy. This study also underscores the importance of integrating CAM education into the medical curricula to address existing knowledge gaps and promote its safe and effective use.

Keywords: *Allopathic doctors, Al Hijamah therapy, Karachi.*

Introduction

Complementary and Alternative Medicine (CAM) encompasses all forms of therapies that fall outside the mainstream of medical practice (World Health Organization, 2021). According to WHO, it has substantial popularity in both developed and developing countries with utilization rates ranging from 50% to 80% (World Health Organization, 2021; Peltzer, & Pengpid, 2018). In a study published in 2018, approximately 51.7% of Pakistan's population chose CAM either separately or in combination with conventional medicine (Ilyas, & Omar, 2020). Al-Hijamah therapy, also known as traditional wet cupping therapy, falls within the category of CAM (Aboushanab, & AlSanad, 2018; Qureshi, et al., 2017; Alrawi, & Fetters, 2012; Khalil, et al., 2018; Al-Bedah, et al., 2019). Muslims believe in this therapy due to its divine nature and practice it as ordered by their final Prophet Muhammad P.B.U.H. (Al-Bedah, et al., 2019; Qureshi, et al., 2017; Alrawi, & Fetters, 2012; Hani, & Saleem, 2019; Kouser, et al., 2021; Allafi, & Al-Haifi, 2020; Kaya, Taşdemir, & Çayır, 2022; Razali, & Muflih, 2021). In the last few decades, due to general population awareness it has become a widespread practice in regions such as China, Europe, United States of America, Asia, Middle East particularly Saudi Arabia and many other countries (Khalil, et al., 2018; Kaya, Taşdemir, & Çayır, 2022; Razali, & Muflih, 2021; Alharbi, et al., 2023; Ghazi, 2016; Al Marshedi, et al., 2019; Al-Yousef, Wajid, & Sales, 2018; Al-Qahtani, & Alsulami, 2023). It is also becoming very popular among the general population of Pakistan (Syahruramdhani, & Fadhlurrahman, 2021).

In recent years, scientific research all over the globe on the effectiveness of cupping in the treatment of various diseases has accelerated and shown proven results (Aboushanab, & AlSanad, 2018; Al-Bedah, et al., 2019; Hani, & Saleem, 2019; Kouser, et al., 2021; Allafi, & Al-Haifi, 2020; Kaya, Taşdemir, & Çayır, 2022; Razali, & Muflih, 2021). It is a safe, noninvasive therapeutic technique that involves single-use disposable cups being placed on targeted anatomical sites. Blood and lymph, among other fluids, are drawn via means of a vacuum and

then bled through superficial skin scratches made by a single-use sterile surgical blade (Al-Bedah, et al., 2019; Hani, & Saleem, 2019; Kouser, et al., 2021; Kaya, Taşdemir, & Çayır, 2022; Razzaq, Khan, & Zehra, 2013).

Despite the increasing interest in Al-Hijamah therapy its acceptance within the medical community is questionable due to lack of scientific research and regulation (Niazi, et al., 2023; Abdullah Al-Rowais, et al., 2012; Syahruramdhani, Taupikurrahman, & Pasha, 2020; El-Mosalami, 2006; Omara, Eldahshan, & Mabrouk, 2013; Azin, Nooraii, & Moshkani, 2010; Iktidar, et al., 2022). Moreover, there are controversies and misconceptions about this therapy (Al-Bedah, et al., 2019; Alharbi, et al., 2023; Ghazi, 2016; Niazi, et al., 2023). Some contend that its perceived effects are attributable to the placebo effect (Al-Bedah, et al., 2019), and concerns have arisen regarding potential risks such as local infections (Rehman, Ul-Ain Baloch, & Awais, 2014), bloodborne diseases (Lee, et al., 2008), and anemia (Khan, 2021). Unqualified practitioners exacerbate these concerns by malpractice and making unsubstantiated claims regarding the efficacy of Hijamah therapy (Al-Bedah, et al., 2019; Al Zaabi, et al., 2023; Tangkiatkumjai, Boardman, & Walker, 2020; Sajid, 2016).

Healthcare professionals including doctors, nurses, and physical therapists, must possess a deeper understanding of Hijamah therapy compared to those outside the healthcare field. This is because they undergo formal education and training in a wide range of medical practices (AlBedah, et al., 2015). They are more likely to have a comprehensive grasp of the benefits, potential risks, and appropriate applications of Hijamah therapy in contrast to individuals without a healthcare background (AlBedah, et al., 2015). But compounding the above challenges, patients frequently refrain from discussing Hijamah therapy with their healthcare providers (Al-Yousef, Wajid, & Sales, 2018; Syahruramdhani, & Fadhlurrahman, 2021), underscoring the pressing need for enhanced awareness and education in this domain. Conversely, in nations such as Saudi Arabia, Bangladesh, United Kingdom, Iran, and Abu

Dhabi, where the government started backing this therapy, there has been a noticeable change in the outlook of healthcare professionals and medical students (Tangkiatkumjai, Boardman, & Walker, 2020; Sajid, 2016; AlBedah, et al., 2015; Buran-Omar, & Alaban, 2022; Al Mansour, et al., 2015).

Rationale

In Pakistan, the public's interest in Hijamah therapy has increased due to its cost-effectivity, relief of symptoms with fewer side effects, and its deep-rooted religious beliefs (Syahruramdhani, & Fadhlurrahman, 2021). This increasing trend of people preferring Hijamah coupled with the lack of knowledge among physicians highlights the need for actions to increase awareness of practicing Hijamah safely and effectively.

Objective

The primary research objective is to assess the awareness, perspectives, and clinical practices associated with al Hijamah therapy among physicians of Karachi, Pakistan. Furthermore, the research aims to establish regulatory bodies for official Hijamah Centers in Pakistan, facilitated by the registered practitioners in a manner that ensures safety and efficacy.

Methodology

Study Design

This is a cross-sectional descriptive survey based on a questionnaire conducted between January 2020 to July 2021 among allopathic doctors working in various hospitals and private clinics in Karachi, Pakistan.

Sample Size

It was calculated using an online sample size calculator of proportion version 3.01 available at www.openepi.com after inserting 68.2% knowledge of Hijamah Practice (Ref. Perception, Attitude, and Knowledge of Nursing Students towards Wet Cupping Therapy (Hijamah) at 7% margin of error and 95% confidence interval we required at least n=170 samples for this study.

Inclusion Criteria

Registered allopathic health care practitioners of no age and gender discrimination of different areas of Karachi practicing at outpatient clinics who have some knowledge about Hijamah therapy.

Exclusion Criteria

Healthcare professionals who decline to take part in the study and possess no familiarity with Hijamah therapy.

Data Collection Procedure

The survey was carried out using a hard copy of the questionnaire for the available doctors and an online questionnaire for the remote doctors. The first part primarily addresses demographic information, the second part explores participants' knowledge and sources of information regarding Hijamah therapy, the third part inquiries about various types of CAM practices, followed by questions regarding perceptions of Hijamah therapy, and lastly, their interest in further learning about Hijamah therapy is assessed. Items mostly of knowledge and attitude in terms of agree, disagree, and not sure answers and some questions regarding their practice of Hijamah therapy in terms of yes or no.

Any query raised by the participant will promptly be clarified by a specified team member. Only 15 minutes are needed to fill out the questionnaire. All the questionnaires will be returned to one of the co-authors who will ensure that all questionnaires are filled out completely.

Ethical Consideration

Information will be given to all participants about the aims and objectives of this study. Any query raised by individual participants was clarified quickly. They will also inform them that this study is without any risk and their identity will remain anonymous. Answering the questionnaire will be considered as informed consent to participate in the study.

Statistical Analysis

The data were stored and analyzed with IBM-SPSS version 23.0. Percentages were utilized to

present the baseline characteristics of the participants under study, which included age group, gender, qualifications, years of practice, and the use of complementary and alternative medicine (CAM). Bar charts and pie charts were employed to visually represent information about CAM, the sources of information about Hijamah therapy, and methods for acquiring knowledge about Hijamah therapy. The knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions of the studied participants regarding Hijamah therapy were reported in terms of counts and percentages.

Results

A total of 182 Allopathic doctors were recruited in this study. 56.6% of the doctors were from

ages 22 to 35 years, mean age was 35.1 (SD=±10.2) years. Among them 78% were females, and 22% were males. 84.6% were found to be MBBS doctors. 53.9% have five or less years of practicing medicine with median years of practice of 5 years.

Among them, 12.6% said that they were also practicing CAM. Delving further into the inquiry unveils that 3.8% of the allopathic doctors practice homeopathy, 3.3% prefer counseling & guidance, 2.7% practice meditations, 2.2% perform massage therapy, 1.6% practice acupressure therapy, 1.6% nutrition therapy, 1.6% spiritual healing, 1.1% acupuncture therapy, 1.1% practice Sujok therapy, 1.1% reported for eastern medicines and 0.5% reported usage of western herbal medicines.

Table 1. Allopathic Doctor's Knowledge and Attitude towards Al Hijamah Therapy

Questions		n	%
Awareness about al Hijamah therapy	Yes	175	96.7
	No	6	3.3
Attain knowledge about al Hijamahtherapy	Yes	131	72.0
	No	51	28.0
Self-experience of al Hijamah	Yes	56	30.8
	No	126	69.2
Referral of patients toHijamah therapists	Yes	63	34.8
	No	118	65.2
Self-Practice of al Hijamah	Yes	103	56.6
	No	79	43.4

Table 2. Shows the Perceptions of Allopathic Doctors about al Hijamah Therapy

Questions	Disagree n (%)	Neutral n (%)	Agree n (%)	I don't know n (%)
A. PERCEPTION ABOUT WHY PATIENT CHOOSE HIJAMAH THERAPY				
It has less side effect	28(15.4)	23(12.6)	94(51.6)	37(20.3)
It is cost effective / economic	25(13.7)	30(16.5)	85(46.7)	42(23.1)
It gives prompt relief from symptoms	35(19.2)	28(15.4)	75(41.2)	44(24.2)
Due to their spiritual / religious belief	13(7.1)	2(1.1)	156(85.7)	11(6)
Due to failure of conventional medicine	41(22.5)	20(11)	96(52.7)	25(13.7)
Due to their peer pressure	61(33.5)	18(9.9)	46(25.3)	57(31.3)
B. OPINION ABOUT THE EFFECTIVENESS OF HIJAMAH THERAPY				
Hijamah therapy is an effective therapy	24(13.2)	17(9.3)	103(56.6)	38(20.9)
Hijama therapy have strong scientific foundation	22(12.1)	18(9.9)	92(50.5)	50(27.5)

Hijamah is a safe practice / not a threat to public health	41(22.5)	15(8.2)	99(54.4)	27(14.8)
Hijamah therapy must be regulated by healthcare authority	19(10.4)	11(6)	132(72.5)	20(11)
Hijamah therapy course must be incorporated into Medical curriculum	28(15.4)	13(7.1)	116(63.7)	25(13.7)
Hijamah therapy must be done only by health care professionals	19(10.4)	12(6.6)	143(78.6)	8(4.4)
Incorporating Hijamah therapy in physician clinic will attract more patients	15(8.2)	18(9.9)	119(65.4)	30(16.5)
Physician gain knowledge about Hijamah therapy leads to better health outcome	23(12.6)	16(8.8)	125(68.7)	18(9.9)
Hijamah therapy replace conventional medicine	79(43.4)	22(12.1)	44(24.2)	37(20.3)
Physician's spiritual beliefs and practice play an important role in health of their patients	25(13.7)	11(6)	127(69.8)	19(10.4)
Hijamah therapy needs lot of research to prove its effectiveness	32(17.6)	17(9.3)	117(64.3)	16(8.8)
There must be a specified center for Hijamah therapy practice	18(9.9)	3(1.6)	150(82.4)	11(6)

Source of information about Hijamah therapy

Figure 1. Shows the Resources and Details to Gather Information about Al- Hijamah Therapy

Figure 2. Shows the Attitude of Doctors towards Learning Resources about Hijamah Therapy

Discussion

Allopathic doctors or physicians play a pivotal role in providing essential healthcare services and medical expertise for the population of Pakistan. This is the first Pakistani study conducted to assess the physician's knowledge and perception about Al-Hijamah therapy. A total of 182 allopathic doctors participated in our study and the mean age was found to be 31.5 years. Physicians having a 5-year experience or less constituted most (53.9%) of our study. In a study in Abu Dhabi by Zaabi et al in 2023, a similar age group was found where 54.5% of physicians were less than 40 years of age and their knowledge about Al-Hijamah therapy was directly proportional to their age and experience. A similar study was carried out in a primary health center in Port Said city of Egypt where 60.7% of the physicians had less than five years of experience in medicine. Another study in Saudi Arabia by Ghazi et al shows no difference between the age and education with knowledge of cupping therapy. In our study a younger age group is more enrolled, which might be due to their habit of exploring new therapies. Studies of Niazi, et al. (2012), Syahruramdhani, Taupikurrahman, and Pasha (2020), Omara, Eldahshan, and Mabrouk (2013), Tangkiatkumjai, Boardman, & Walker, (2020) also show a female predominance which is consistent with our study.

According to a study conducted in the UK, the average prevalence of use of CAM by physicians was 20.6% (AlBedah, et al., 2015), an Iranian study also reported that 9.9% of physicians practiced CAM (Azin, Nooraii, & Moshkani, 2010). A study in Bangladesh on medical students' perception of CAM was found in favor of learning different CAM practices including Hijamah therapy (Iktidar, et al., 2022). This aligns with our study where 12.6% of participants said they are also practicing CAM.

An Egyptian study on health science students reported that more than 80% of the physicians had good knowledge regarding CAM including Al Hijamah (Omara, Eldahshan, & Mabrouk, 2013). In the UAE study by Zaabi et al, 67.6%

of the respondents had adequate knowledge (Tangkiatkumjai, Boardman, & Walker, 2020). A study performed in Saudi Arabia reported that 70% of doctors are familiar with cupping therapy (Niazi, et al., 2021; Al Mansour, et al., 2015). Furthermore, a study conducted on medical students in Bangladesh in the year 2022 to assess their knowledge attitude, and practices about CAM revealed that 43.4% of students had heard of Hijamah/Cupping therapy but didn't have any knowledge (Iktidar, et al., 2022). Indonesian study among nurses shows possession of average knowledge of Hijamah therapy (Syahruramdhani, Taupikurrahman, & Pasha, 2020). It is strangely observed that 96.7% of the Pakistani physicians in our study also have sufficient knowledge about Hijamah therapy and half of them agreed that Hijamah therapy has a strong scientific foundation. 54% agreed that Hijamah is a safe practice and not a threat to the public.

In our study, the source of information on Al Hijamah therapy was mostly from their relatives and friends. Only 24.7% were informed by their patients and 24.7% of Physicians sought information from literature, seminars, and social media. In a study conducted on Bangladeshi and Egyptian medical students, their most utilized sources of information were friends and mass media (El-Mosalami, 2006; Iktidar, et al., 2022).

In our study, 85.7% of respondents concurred that patients opt for Hijamah therapy primarily because of their spiritual or religious convictions. Moreover, they (69.8 %) also had a belief that physician's spiritual beliefs and practice play an important role in the health of their patients. This observation aligns with the Karachi study on public awareness of Hijamah therapy, where individuals often chose this therapy due to religious convictions (Syahruramdhani, & Fadhlurrahman, 2021). This insight sheds light on the significance and extensive utilization of Al-Hijamah in Saudi Arabia and other Muslim communities where particular emphasis is placed on this religious therapy.

Many researchers including health care practitioners exhibited a favorable attitude toward the effectiveness of cupping therapy worldwide, consistent with our study finding where 56.6% of the physicians agreed that Hijamah is an effective therapy. More than half of our study respondents agreed that gaining Hijamah therapy knowledge will lead to better health outcomes. 56.6% of the doctors want to learn and practice Hijamah therapy and are interested in reading relevant books and attending conferences and seminars. They are also in favor of incorporating Hijamah therapy into physician's clinics, this will attract more patients which is consistent with other studies where physicians have the opinion that this therapy helps conventional medicine and improves health outcome (Tangkiatkumjai, Boardman, & Walker, 2020; Sajid, 2016; Al Mansour, et al., 2015). Research conducted this year in Abu Dhabi reported that 66.9% of participants held a positive view of cupping therapy (Tangkiatkumjai, Boardman, & Walker, 2020). A positive perception of Hijamah also exists in undergraduate medical students of Bangladesh (Iktidar, et al., 2022) and Indonesia (Syahruramdhani, Taupikurrahman, & Pasha, 2020).

On the contrary, only 34.8% of doctors referred their patients to a Hijamah therapist and 65.2% of physicians did not recommend their patients to use Hijamah therapy. Karachi's public awareness study is also consistent with the same opinion. In a Saudi study only 54.8% of the patients discussed Hijamah therapy with their doctor (Alharbi, et al., 2023; Al-Yousef, Wajid, & Sales, 2018; Al-Qahtani, & Alsulami, 2023; Syahruramdhani, & Fadhlurrahman, 2021). Iranian study reported that 24% of physicians referred their patients to Al Hijamah therapy (Azin, Nooraii, & Moshkani, 2010). UAE study found that a limited number of physicians refer or counsel their patients for Hijamah (Tangkiatkumjai, Boardman, & Walker, 2020) concurrent with the general population's survey most of them never discussed complementary medicine with their physicians (Al Marshedi, et al., 2019). These findings are not surprising since teaching about CAM modalities like Hijamah is

not included in the medical curriculum in many countries including Pakistan (Iktidar, et al., 2022; Buran-Omar, & Alaban, 2022; Al Mansour, et al., 2015).

The practice of Al Hijamah therapy among physicians around the globe reveals that only in Saudi Arabia 75% of hospital employees displayed a high degree of CT expertise and implemented it into their practice and this incidence has increased since the last decade (Al-Qahtani, & Alsulami, 2023; Alharbi, et al., 2023; Sajid, 2016). In UAE two-thirds of practicing physicians reported poor practice even though Hijamah therapy was registered by their government 10 years ago (Tangkiatkumjai, Boardman, & Walker, 2020). 92.7% of medical students in Bangladesh reported that they had never undergone Hijamah therapy (Iktidar, et al., 2022) same practice was noticed in Tehran (Azin, Nooraii, & Moshkani, 2010), Cairo (Omara, Eldahshan, & Mabrouk, 2013) and Indonesia among healthcare practitioners (Omara, Eldahshan, & Mabrouk, 2013). In our study, more than half of the doctors reported poor practice of Hijamah therapy and only 30.8% of doctors had experienced Hijamah personally.

In our study, 63.7% of respondents expressed their agreement with the necessity of incorporating Hijamah therapy courses into the medical curriculum and 72% are in favor of it being regulated by the government. The majority also have the opinion that Hijamah needs a lot of research. There should be a specified center for its practice, and it must be done by trained healthcare practitioners. Studies conducted in Tehran, Cairo, Egypt, Bangladesh, and Abu Dhabi support this fact in which the overall physicians had a positive attitude toward the usefulness of complementary methods however they needed to improve their knowledge. In Zaabi's study, more than 50% of respondents agreed that educating physicians about cupping therapy is necessary (Tangkiatkumjai, Boardman, & Walker, 2020). A study in Cairo Egypt and Tehran had similar results, more than 70% of physicians encouraged the introduction of cupping in the curriculum of medicine as a scientific issue (El-Mosalami, 2006; Omara,

Eldahshan, & Mabrouk, 2013; Azin, Nooraii, & Moshkani, 2010). Other studies such as one in Bangladesh and Indonesia highlight a lack of government support for CAM (Syahruramdhani, Taupikurrahman, & Pasha, 2020; Azin, Nooraii, & Moshkani, 2010). According to a systemic review from multiple countries regarding the use of CAM including British health practice found that integrating (CAM) into the curriculum is of utmost importance because the primary barrier preventing and recommending CAM is the lack of evidence supporting CAM practices.

Conclusion

Our research findings suggest that physicians have a sound understanding of cupping therapy and maintain a positive outlook toward it. Despite their positive attitude and knowledge in this field, physicians encounter obstacles in effectively employing, recommending, or advising/referring cupping therapy. This study also underscores the importance of integrating CAM education into medical curricula to address existing knowledge gaps and promote its safe and effective use.

Future Research

To address this issue, we can propose future research to identify the common factors that present as a barrier to medical counseling on Hijamah therapy.

Further high-quality research is needed to explore the false beliefs about cupping therapy among healthcare professionals and practitioners together with the availability of standard clinical practice guidelines for Hijamah (wet cupping therapy).

Limitations

Only a limited number of doctors agreed to take part in this study so it may not be representative of the entire population. The absence of government regulation for Hijamah therapy can also be seen as a limitation, as it affects the willingness of doctors to share their knowledge.

High lights and acknowledgement

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